

Phosphoinositides in the control of lysosome function and homeostasis

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Abstract

Lysosomes are the main degradative compartments of mammalian cells and serve as platforms for cellular nutrient signaling and sterol transport. The diverse functions of lysosomes and their adaptation to extracellular and intracellular cues are tightly linked to the spatiotemporally controlled synthesis, turnover and interconversion of lysosomal phosphoinositides, minor phospholipids that define membrane identity and couple membrane dynamics to cell signaling. How precisely lysosomal phosphoinositides act and which effector proteins within the lysosome membrane or at the lysosomal surface recognize them is only now beginning to emerge. Importantly, mutations in phosphoinositide metabolizing enzyme cause lysosomal dysfunction and are associated with numerous diseases ranging from neurodegeneration to cancer. Here we discuss the phosphoinositides and phosphoinositide metabolizing enzymes implicated in lysosome function and homeostasis and outline perspectives for future research.

Introduction

Lysosomes have long been regarded solely as a degradative compartment in eukaryotic cells. However, in recent years it has become clear that lysosomes fulfil multiple other functions including a central role as a metabolic signaling hub that integrates nutrient sensing and metabolic adaptation, termination of growth factor receptor signaling (1), protein and organellar quality control by serving as the degradative endpoint of the autophagy pathway, transport of sterols and other lipids, and in plasma membrane repair (2). Moreover, specialized lysosomes -

commonly referred to as lysosome-related organelles (LROs, see ref. (3) for a comprehensive recent review) - execute secretory functions in the skin (melanosomes) and in the immune system (lytic granules) (4) and in presynaptic biogenesis in developing nerve cells (5). Whether all or some of the features and functions of lysosomes described here also apply to LROs will have to await further studies. The diverse functions of lysosomes require their continuous communication with other subcellular compartments, e.g. with the early endosomal system and the Golgi complex, and with the cell environment to enable their rapid functional adjustment to changing cell physiological conditions. Lysosomes overlap in function and are notoriously hard to distinguish from late endosomes, acidic organelles that target internalized cargo for lysosomal proteolysis. In this review we refer to late endocytic degradative and acidic compartments as lysosomes.

Work in recent years has unraveled crucial roles for phosphoinositides (PIPs), minor phospholipids that define membrane identity and couple membrane dynamics to cell signaling, and PIP-metabolizing enzymes in the control of lysosomal function, dynamics, and homeostasis. Eukaryotic cells comprise seven different species of PIPs that are distinguished by the phosphorylation pattern at positions 3, 4, and 5 of their inositol ring. Approximately 90 PIP kinases and phosphatases interconvert the various PIP species into one another in humans. Phosphorylated PIPs are mostly thought to act as organelle-specific recruitment factors and/ or as allosteric activators of effector proteins to which they bind, thereby regulating cell physiological function (6-9).

Lysosomes harbor a diverse complement of PIPs (Figure 1). In addition to phosphatidylinositol 3-phosphate (PI(3)P), which dominates the endosomal system, lysosomes have been shown to contain or be regulated by phosphatidylinositol 3,5-bisphosphate (PI(3,5)P₂) and, possibly phosphatidylinositol 5-phosphate (PI(5)P), PIP species thought to be specific to lysosomes, late endosomes, and other lysosome-related organelles (see the excellent recent review by (10) for further information). Surprisingly, lysosomes also harbor minor pools of phosphatidylinositol 4-phosphate (PI(4)P) and phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PI(4,5)P₂), lipids most highly enriched at the Golgi complex and at the plasma membrane, respectively, and, phosphatidylinositol 3,4-bisphosphate (PI(3,4)P₂), a rare PIP species that may control lysosome function in response to cell signaling. At present it is unclear why lysosomes contain so many different PIP species and whether and how different PIP pools may correlate with the functional state and/ or the intracellular distribution of lysosomes within cells. While specific sets of PIP species likely are required to execute the manifold functions of lysosomes in eukaryotic cells, a non-exclusive alternative possibility is that distinct subsets of

lysosomal organelles, e.g. peripheral vs acidic perinuclear lysosomes or lysosomes arising from distinct membrane fusion events, contain distinct PIP species. In addition to late endosomes that are thought to mature into *bona fide* lysosomes by acquisition of degradative lysosomal enzymes via post-Golgi carriers, terminal storage lysosomes, endolysosomes (i.e. terminal storage lysosomes fused with late endosomes), autolysosomes (i.e. autophagosomes fused with lysosomes), and proto-lysosomes (i.e. newly formed lysosomes pinched off from autolysosome tubules) have been described (11). Whether these subtypes of lysosomes can be distinguished by their PIP content is uncertain as we currently lack reliable probes to monitor all biologically relevant PIP species (e.g. no probes exist for detecting PI(3,5)P₂) in living cells. The identification of novel specific PIP-binding effector proteins paired with new labeling and targeting strategies may solve this problem in the future.

So far, much of our understanding of lysosomal PIP biology has been derived from the genetic, biochemical, and cell biological study of PIP metabolizing enzymes and their roles in human diseases related to lysosome dysfunction (Table 1) (9), further highlighting the paramount importance of lysosomal PIPs in physiology. Here we summarize the current state of knowledge derived from these studies and outline perspectives for future research.

A signaling network of lysosomal PIPs, mTORC1 and TFEB

Lysosomes are essential platforms for the coordination of signaling pathways that regulate cell metabolism and growth (1). Growth factor signaling and the availability of energy and nutrients converge on the metabolic master regulator mTORC1 (12), a multiprotein assembly comprised of mTOR kinase, Raptor (regulatory associated protein of mTOR), mammalian LST (lethal with SEC13) 8, PRAS40 (proline-rich Akt substrate of 40 kDa), and DEPTOR (DEP domain-containing mTOR-interacting protein) recruited to lysosomes by the Rag small GTPases in response to cellular and lysosomal amino acid status. mTORC1 integrates these signals and balances catabolic with anabolic pathways, that is autophagy with the synthesis of proteins, lipids and nucleotides. Disruptions in mTORC1-mediated lysosomal signaling are implicated in diseases such as diabetes, cancer and neurological disorders (12). The activity of mTORC1 is closely linked to the functional status of its resident organelle, the lysosome (11). A direct substrate of mTORC1 is the transcription factor EB (TFEB), which, together with its close cousins transcription factor E3 (TFE3) and microphthalmia-associated transcription factor (MITF), regulates the transcription of many lysosomal and autophagy genes (13) and is inactivated by mTORC1-mediated phosphorylation (14). mTORC1 is regulated by lysosomal PIPs, e.g. PI(3)P, PI(3,4)P₂, and PI(3,5)P₂, and together with TFEB these factors

form a regulatory network that couples cellular lysosome homeostasis with internal and external cues (Figure 2a).

The PI(3)P generating kinase VPS34 is required for full activation of mTORC1, e.g. during refeeding post-starvation (15, 16). While the exact mechanism by which PI(3)P activates mTORC1 is unclear, it appears that the PI(3)P-mediated induction of mTORC1 activity requires the formation of membrane contact sites between lysosomes and the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) (17). Specifically, amino acid stimulation was shown to trigger the recruitment of the PI(3)P-binding protein FYVE and coiled-coiled domain-containing protein 1 (FYCO1) to lysosomes, which leads to contacts between FYCO1-decorated lysosomes and the ER via the PI(3)P effector protein Protrudin. Protrudin is an ER resident protein and - similar to FYCO1 - associates with lysosomes by coincidence detection of PI(3)P and Rab7 (18). Given that Protrudin binds to PI(4,5)P₂, PI(3,4)P₂ and PI(3,4,5)P₃ with preference over PI(3)P, at least *in vitro* (19) it is conceivable that PIPs other than PI(3)P contribute to the association of Protrudin with lysosomes. Loss of either Protrudin or FYCO1 represses mTORC1 activity, while increasing the levels of active TFEB in the nucleus (17), highlighting the close ties of PIPs, mTORC1, and lysosome homeostasis. Interestingly, depletion of the putative PI(3)P phosphatase MTMR4 (Myotubularin Related Protein 4) has been shown to increase lysosomal PI(3)P levels and inhibit the nuclear translocation of TFEB without affecting mTORC1 (20), suggesting that PI(3)P may also regulate TFEB activity via mTORC1-independent pathways.

While PI(3)P produced by the class III phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase VPS34 upregulates mTORC1, PI(3,4)P₂ generated by the class II phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase PI3KC2β plays an opposing role. In growth factor deprived conditions PI3KC2β is recruited to the mTORC1 subunit Raptor on lysosomes and phosphorylates PI(4)P to generate PI(3,4)P₂. Increased PI(3,4)P₂ levels recruit 14-3-3 proteins to Raptor, which leads to the inactivation of mTORC1 (21). Furthermore, as discussed below, PI(3,4)P₂ facilitates cholesterol transport from lysosomes to the ER via the activation of the sterol transporter oxysterol-binding protein-related protein 1L (ORP1L) (22). Low levels of lysosomal cholesterol also inhibit mTORC1 activity and induce TFEB nuclear translocation (23), identifying lysosomal PI(3,4)P₂ as a negative regulator of the mTORC1-TFEB axis.

Besides mTORC1 signaling, multiple other pathways have evolved to regulate lysosomal homeostasis via TFEB nuclear-cytosolic shuttling (24). PI(3,5)P₂, the product of the PIP 5-kinase PIKfyve complex (comprising PIKfyve kinase, the scaffold Vac14, and the putative phosphatase Fig4), constitutes a lysosomal signature PIP as interference with its metabolism has grave consequences for multiple aspects of lysosomal function (25). Inhibition of PIKfyve

activity induces the nuclear translocation of TFEB and the induction of lysosomal gene expression via a pathway that depends on Ca^{2+} but is independent of mTORC1 (26-28). During nutrient starvation, the activity of the PI(3,5)P₂-activated lysosomal Ca^{2+} release channel Mucolipin-1 (MCOLN1, also known as TRPML1) (29) rapidly increases and the ensuing Ca^{2+} release through MCOLN1 locally activates the phosphatase calcineurin that dephosphorylates TFEB, enabling its nuclear translocation and activation (30). At least in yeast, PI(3,5)P₂ like PI(3)P also promotes mTORC1 activation through direct binding of the mTORC1 subunit Raptor, (31, 32).

Taken together, lysosomal PI 3-phosphates such as PI(3)P, PI(3,4)P₂, and PI(3,5)P₂ couple mTORC1 activity to the transcriptional regulation of lysosomal and autophagy genes via TFEB and TFEB family proteins to control lysosome homeostasis.

PIPs in the control of lysosome positioning and dynamics

Lysosomes are highly motile organelles that cycle between the perinuclear area and the cell periphery by microtubule-based transport via kinesins (e.g. kinesin 1/ KIF5 and kinesin 3/ KIF1A/B β) and dynein. Lysosomal transport and re-positioning appear to be an adaptation mechanism to changing environmental conditions. Growth factors (33), nutrient availability (34) or extracellular pH (35) trigger the re-positioning of lysosomes and this appears to be crucial for nearly all aspects of lysosome function as described in detail in (36, 37).

PIP metabolizing enzymes regulate both the anterograde (i.e. to the microtubule plus end in the cell periphery) and retrograde (i.e. to the microtubule organizing center in the perinuclear area) lysosome transport (Figure 2a). Net retrograde transport appears to be facilitated by PI3KC2 β , which in response to growth factor starvation translocates to lysosomes and converts PI(4)P into PI(3,4)P₂. Elevated PI(3,4)P₂ levels, by a so far unknown mechanism, induce the perinuclear accumulation of lysosomes and mTORC1 repression (21). Little is known about the specific effectors of lysosomal PI(3,4)P₂ that could mediate this effect. It is possible that PI(3,4)P₂ directly or indirectly affects the activation cycle of small GTPases that link lysosomes to dynein or kinesin motors including ADP-ribosylation factor like 8 (Arl8) (38, 39), a switch for lysosomal kinesin association, and Rab7, which may connect to either dynein or kinesin motors (40-42) (see below). Another candidate is ORP1L, a lysosomal lipid shuttling protein that binds to PI(3,4)P₂ (22) and promotes retrograde transport of lysosomes (43) by a so far unknown mechanism, possibly involving the regulation of lysosomal sterol levels.

Conversely, anterograde transport of lysosomes critically depends on PI(3)P synthesized by the mTORC1-regulated (44, 45) class III phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase VPS34

and on membrane contact sites (MCS) between lysosomes and the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) (18, 43, 46, 47). In this mechanism, the ER-resident membrane protein Protrudin associates with lysosomal PI(3)P via its FYVE domain and with Rab7 at ER-lysosome MCS (18). These MCS then mediate the transfer of kinesin 1 from Protrudin to the motor adaptor FYCO1 on lysosomes to promote their microtubule-dependent translocation to the cell periphery (18) and the concomitant activation of mTORC1 (17). Interestingly, mutations in FYCO1 cause congenital cataracts in humans (48) (Table 1), suggesting that aberrant FYCO1-dependent lysosome positioning may cause disease.

A second mechanism by which PI(3)P could promote lysosome dispersion may involve the generation of PI(3,5)P₂ from PI(3)P by the lysosomal "signature PIP enzyme" PIKfyve. One of the multiple consequences of PI(3,5)P₂ loss for lysosome biology is altered lysosome transport and positioning. Neurons depleted of PIKfyve or sustained pharmacological inhibition of PIKfyve stalls lysosome movement in neurites (49). In contrast, short-term PIKfyve inhibition has been reported to promote the peripheral dispersion of lysosomes as a result of impaired PI(3,5)P₂-MCOLN1-dynein signaling (50). How these seemingly contradictory findings can be reconciled has to await further analysis. In any case these findings suggest an important function for PI(3,5)P₂ in regulating lysosome dynamics, while the mechanisms and effector proteins that couple PI(3,5)P₂ to the machinery for lysosome transport remain to be discovered.

Whether and how these mechanisms intersect with the reported lysosomal recruitment of kinesins 1 (39) and 3 (51, 52) by active Arl8•GTP and its effector protein SifA-kinesin interacting protein (SKIP, also known as PLEKHM2) (39) remains to be determined. The kinesin 3 KIF1B β and the kinesin 1 adaptor SKIP contain putative lipid-binding pleckstrin homology (PH) domains that conceivably could bind to lysosomal PIPs including PI(3)P (53). Alternatively, lysosomal PI 3-phosphates may regulate Arl8 activity via impacting on the BLOC-1-related complex (BORC) required for Arl8 recruitment to the lysosomal surface (51) and/ or by regulating Arl8 GEF or GAP activities.

Dissecting the interplay between these factors and their regulation by lysosomal PIPs as well as the interplay between lysosome position, ER-lysosome MCS formation (46, 54), and nutrient signaling via mTORC1 remain fruitful areas for future studies.

PIPs regulate lysosomal sterol transport via membrane contact sites

Lysosomes form extensive MCS with the ER (46, 54) and these contacts seem to be essential for several aspects of lysosome biology. Apart from the regulation of mTORC1 signaling and lysosome dynamics, a main function of ER-lysosome MCS is the non-vesicular

transport of sterols from lysosomes to the ER (Figure 2b). Cholesterol is an important constituent of cellular membranes, regulating membrane fluidity, signaling, and vesicle trafficking (55). LDL-Cholesterol that reaches the lysosome via the endocytic pathway is hydrolyzed in the lysosomal lumen to generate free cholesterol. Subsequently, cholesterol is transported to the limiting membrane of lysosomes through Niemann-Pick C1 (NPC1) and Niemann-Pick C2 (NPC2) (56). From the lysosome donor membrane oxysterol-binding proteins (ORPs) transfer cholesterol to acceptor organelles in a PIP-dependent manner. The Rab7-binding (57) lipid transfer protein ORP1L acts as a transporter for cholesterol from the lysosome to the ER (58). Cholesterol transport by ORP1L depends on MCS formation via ER-localized VAMP-Associated Protein A/B (VAP-A/B) and is stimulated by PI(3,4)P₂ and/ or PI(4,5)P₂. KO of ORP1L impaired the removal of cholesterol from lysosomes and this defect is phenocopied by depletion of PI3KC2β (22), a lipid kinase that locally produces PI(3,4)P₂ at lysosomes under conditions of starvation (21).

Multiple other proteins involved in lysosomal lipid transfer appear to be regulated by PIPs as well: For example, on the lysosomal surface ORP1L interacts with oxysterol binding protein-related protein 2 (ORP2) (59), a lipid transfer protein that facilitates delivery of cholesterol to the plasma membrane in exchange for PI(4,5)P₂ (60). This function depends on the ability of ORP2 to associate with PIPs (59). Likewise, the ER-localized protein oxysterol binding protein-related protein 5 (ORP5) interacts with lysosomal NPC1, a protein mutated in the lysosomal cholesterol storage disorder Niemann Pick disease type C in humans, and directly or indirectly (e.g. via its activity on plasma membrane PI(4)P and phosphatidylserine (61)) promotes cholesterol transport from lysosomes to the ER (62). This function depends on ORP5 binding to PI(4,5)P₂ via its PH domain. These studies establish a role for lysosomal PIPs in cholesterol transfer between lysosomes and the ER.

PIPs regulate autophagosome/ lysosome fusion

Lysosomes are well known degradative organelles of mammalian cells. They receive cargo from the endocytic and autophagic pathways (63) by fusion of late endosomes and autophagosomes to enable substrate degradation in the lysosome lumen. Lysosomal degradation is mediated by hydrolases that operate at acidic pH established by the v-ATPase, which requires association with PI(3,5)P₂ for assembly (64). Moreover, PIPs control the tethering and SNARE-mediated fusion of lysosomes with autophagosomes (65, 66) via multiple, so far incompletely understood mechanisms (Figure 2C).

Autophagosomes are enriched in PI(3)P generated by the VPS34-complex I (comprised of VPS34, VPS15, BECLIN 1, ATG14L) (67), while on lysosomes a fraction of PI(3)P synthesized by VPS34-complex II (comprised of VPS34, VPS15, BECLIN 1, UVRAG) is phosphorylated to PI(3,5)P₂ by the PIKfyve complex (i.e. PIKfyve, Vac14, Fig4), a reaction that is counteracted by the PI(3,5)P₂ 5-phosphatase INPP5E. Inhibition or loss of either PIKfyve or INPP5E, an enzyme mutated in Joubert syndrome in humans (Table 1), lead to defects in lysosomal fusion events including autophagosome/ lysosome fusion (50, 68). The fusion of autophagosomes with lysosomes is thought to be initiated by the PI(3)P-dependent recruitment of TECtonin β-Propeller Repeat containing 1 (TECPR1) protein to autophagosomes, which via coincident binding of the ATG12-ATG5 complex tethers autophagosomes to lysosomes (69) as a prerequisite for fusion mediated by the SNARE proteins syntaxin17, Snap29, Vamp7/8, and Ykt6 (70). SNARE-mediated autophagosome-lysosome fusion appears to be aided by the PI(3)P-dependent stabilization of actin filaments on lysosomes mediated by cortactin (71, 72). Furthermore, autophagosome/ lysosome fusion requires MCOLN1, a lysosomal calcium release channel whose activity depends on PI(3,5)P₂ (29). Other potential PI(3,5)P₂ effectors that may directly or indirectly affect lysosomal fusion events include the v-ATPase (64), the sodium-conducting twin pore channel 2 (TPC2) (73), and the lysosomal PX-domain protein Sorting Nexin 14 (SNX14) (74). Truncating mutations of SNX14 cause familial cerebellar atrophy (Table 1) and patient cells display defects in autophagosome clearance (74), suggesting that SNX14 could mediate autophagosome/ lysosome fusion. These data suggest that the fusion of autophagosomes and lysosomes is controlled by intricately balanced levels of lysosomal PI(3)P and PI(3,5)P₂.

Apart from autophagosomal PI(3)P and PI(3,5)P₂ on the lysosomal membrane, autophagosome/ lysosome fusion also requires the ordered synthesis and turnover of PI(4)P and PI(4,5)P₂. Phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase type IIα (PI4KIIα) is present on lysosomes (75) and can be recruited to autophagosomes via association with GABARAP during starvation (76). Synthesis of PI(4)P on both of these membranes is required for fusion (76). On lysosomes PI(4)P can be further phosphorylated to PI(4,5)P₂ by phosphatidylinositol 4-phosphate 5-kinase type Iγ (PIPKIγ) (75). PI(4,5)P₂ may lead to the inactivation of Rab7 by an hitherto unknown mechanism thereby triggering the release of the Rab7 effector PLEKHM1 from lysosomes which allows autophagosome/ lysosome fusion to proceed (75). Besides the production of PI(4,5)P₂, PIPKIγ also acts as a scaffold by recruiting the ATG14 component of the VPS34 complex I to autophagosomes (77). ATG14 directly binds to PI(4,5)P₂ and PI(4,5)P₂ availability regulates

ATG14-VPS34 complex assembly (77). Lysosomal PI(4,5)P₂ likely needs to be restricted to nanodomains that are kept separate from those containing MCOLN1, which is potently inhibited by PI(4,5)P₂ (78). Such PI(4,5)P₂ nanodomains may be generated by oculocerebrorenal syndrome of Lowe (OCRL) 5-phosphatase-mediated PI(4,5)P₂-hydrolysis (79) (Table 1; Figure 2C).

From these data a model emerges whereby parallel pathways of PI(3)P/ PI(3,5)P₂ and PI(4)P/ PI(4,5)P₂ synthesis and turnover control distinct, yet poorly characterized, steps in the formation of autolysosomes. Similar reactions may govern the fusion of late endosomes with lysosomes. Future studies will need to address the molecular machineries that recognize distinct PIP lipids during the tethering and fusion reactions of late endosomes or autophagosomes with lysosomes.

PIPs control lysosome homeostasis and reformation

Lysosomes are subject to high turnover and plasticity. For example, autophagosomes fuse with lysosomes to degrade their engulfed material, a process that consumes a large portion of lysosomes (80). Similarly, lysosomes frequently fuse with the plasma membrane (4), which over time decreases the pool of functional lysosomes. On the other hand, endosomal trafficking increases lysosomal membrane content as late endosomes continuously fuse with and mature to degradative lysosomes. Apart from these membrane fluxes, lysosomal membrane proteins and luminal degradative enzymes need to be replenished. Endolysosomal membrane and protein homeostasis mechanisms therefore must be adapted to the rates of trafficking, fusion, and secretion. These rates depend on the extracellular environment, e.g. on nutrients (1) and on pH (81). PIPs regulate both lysosomal membrane and protein homeostasis and may act as major signal transducers that convey environmental cues to the lysosomal compartment. Apart from the TFEB lysosome-to-nucleus signaling pathway discussed above, several other PIP-dependent mechanisms exist to maintain lysosomal homeostasis.

PI(4)P plays a key role in the trafficking of newly synthesized lysosomal enzymes from the TGN to maturing lysosomes via sorting of the mannose 6-phosphate receptors (MPRs) (4, 82). For example, the PI 4-kinase isozymes phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase III β (PI4KIII β) and II α (PI4KII α) are necessary for the lysosomal delivery of β -glucocerebrosidase (GBA) (83), an acidic hydrolase mutated in Gaucher's disease in humans (Table 1). PI4KII α also associates with several components of protein complexes mutated in Hermanski-Pudlak syndrome (Table 1) that are required for the motor protein-dependent trafficking of lysosomes and lysosome-related organelles such as melanosomes or lytic granules in T cells of the immune system (84).

To balance lysosomal membrane homeostasis, lysosomes and autolysosomes tubulate and bud off new nascent proto-lysosomes, i.e. small and immature lysosomes that are believed to mature and replenish the pool of functional lysosomes (80). This process of (auto-) lysosome tubulation and budding off of nascent proto-lysosomes was termed autophagic lysosome reformation (ALR) (Figure 2C,D). Tubulation of (auto-) lysosomes has been observed by live imaging and electron microscopy in several cell types and, thus appears to be a ubiquitous process, while nascent proto-lysosomes so far have been studied mainly in NRK cells. Although many details of ALR remain to be defined recent data suggest that multiple lysosomal PIP species, e.g. PI(4)P, PI(3)P, PI(3,5)P₂, and PI(4,5)P₂ (Figure 2d) may act at distinct stages of the process. Of these, arguably the role of PI(4,5)P₂ is best understood: PI(4,5)P₂ is synthesized on autolysosomes and lysosomal tubules upon prolonged starvation by phosphatidylinositol 4-phosphate 5-kinase type I (PIP5K) isoforms, i.e. at a time when ALR commences. PI(4,5)P₂ facilitates the formation of lysosomal tubules by recruitment of the kinesin 1 KIF5B (85) and further triggers the assembly of a clathrin/ AP-2 coat that mediates the budding of proto-lysosomes from these tubular intermediates (86), followed by OCRL-mediated PI(4,5)P₂ hydrolysis (79).

Surprisingly, synthesis of the PI(4,5)P₂ precursor PI(4)P by PI4KIIIβ appears to be a negative regulator of lysosome tubulation. PI4KIIIβ is mainly active at the Golgi complex, however, a minor fraction also localizes to lysosomes (87). Depletion of PI4KIIIβ is sufficient to induce lysosome tubulation even in fed cells (87, 88) arguing that PI4KIIIβ and PI(4)P either prevent tubule formation in nutrient replete conditions or that their dissolution by budding of proto-lysosomes is perturbed. ALR may therefore be a constitutive process that is further stimulated by prolonged starvation. Together, these findings suggest that PI(4)P on lysosomes may not be a mere substrate for PI(4,5)P₂ generation but that it has signaling functions in its own right.

In the final step of proto-lysosome formation vesicles pinch off from lysosome tubules by membrane scission, a process regulated by PI(3)P. PI(3)P on lysosomes is produced by the VPS34 complex II comprising VPS34, VPS15, BECLIN1, and UVRAG (89). mTORC1 enhances VPS34 activity by phosphorylating UVRAG and thereby boosts lysosomal PI(3)P levels (45). Interference with UVRAG phosphorylation by mTORC1 or with PI(3)P generation causes lysosome tubules to persist even in nutrient replete conditions, suggesting that PI(3)P synthesis on proto-lysosomes is required for fission. Similar phenotypes are observed upon genetic or pharmacological interference with the function of the fissioning GTPase dynamin 2, suggesting that dynamin 2 may mediate the scission of nascent lysosomes from lysosomal tubules (90). As

the PH domain of dynamin 2 prefers to bind to PI(4,5)P₂ over PI(3)P (91) the question if and how PI(3)P and dynamin 2 cooperate in proto-lysosome formation remains to be answered. A potential effector of PI(3)P in ALR is the FYVE domain-containing protein Spastizin (also called ZYVE26 or FYVE-CENT) that is mutated in Hereditary Spastic paraplegia (HSP) in humans (Table 1) and facilitates the formation of lysosomal tubules (88). Spastizin binds to both PI(3)P (92) and to the VPS34 complex II, an association that is disrupted by HSP patient mutations (93). Spastizin may, thus, regulate the generation of its membrane anchor PI(3)P, providing a positive feedback loop for ALR. How a PI(3)P-dependent role for Spastizin in lysosomal tubule formation can be reconciled with a requirement for VPS34-mediated PI(3)P production in proto-lysosome fission has to await further studies.

Finally, ALR requires production of PI(3,5)P₂. PIKfyve inhibition by YM201636 inhibits starvation-induced lysosome tubulation (50), while tubulation and budding of nascent proto-lysosomes resumes during washout of the drug (94). A potential PI(3,5)P₂ effector is MCOLN1, although its role remains controversial (50, 94). Several other putative effectors of PI(3,5)P₂ in lysosomes have been identified including the v-ATPase (64) and the sodium selective twin pore channel 2 (TPC2) (73). Whether the association of these factors with PI(3,5)P₂ plays a role in ALR and/ or other lysosome functions remains to be addressed.

Perspectives

• **Importance of the field:** In the last decades we have witnessed a cornucopia of insights into lysosome biology including their roles in autophagy, nutrient sensing by mTORC1, their roles in neurodegenerative diseases, and the gene transcriptional pathways that couple the autophagy/lysosome pathway to cell physiology. Rather than representing merely the unglamorous trash bin of the cell, lysosomes have turned out to be functionally remarkably versatile organelles. This versatility is reflected by the diversity and plasticity of their PIP content and the multitude of lysosomal PIP metabolizing enzymes. The frequent association of these enzymes with genetic diseases (9) impressively underscores the importance of PIP signaling on lysosomes (Table 1) for human physiology.

• **Summary of current thinking:** Much of our present efforts have been directed at the genetic or pharmacological targeting of lipid kinases that regulate lysosome function and homeostasis, while comparably little is known about the PIP phosphatases, for example the large family of myotubularin 3-phosphatases that hydrolyze PI(3)P and PI(3,5)P₂ and, indirectly, may control other PIP lipids, and thereby, lysosome function (20). Phosphatases are often expressed at low

levels and difficult to target by pharmacological approaches. With the advent of genome engineering and novel chemical-genetic approaches insights into the lipid phosphatases that control lysosome biology will hopefully gain a boost.

• **Future directions:** A major gap in our understanding is the analysis of the PIP binding effector proteins that carry out and coordinate the complex interplay between the various PIPs at work in the regulation of lysosome function, dynamics, and homeostasis. Their identification is often hampered by the fact that some lysosomal PIP lipids such as PI(3,5)P₂ and PI(3,4)P₂ are present at very low levels and/ or are enriched in tiny nanodomains that are difficult to visualize with conventional microscopy techniques. As a result, the PIP-associated effector proteins are difficult to detect in situ or in living cells and their presence in discrete nanodomains is aided by coincident devices, for example small G proteins to which they bind. Given the prominent lysosomal defects elicited by manipulating PIP lipids such as PI(3,5)P₂ and the severity of human diseases associated with defective lysosomal PIP metabolism clearly warrants new efforts to fill this important gap in lysosome biology. Systematic interaction studies (95) and comparative (sub)proteomic approaches may pave the way to the discovery of novel PIP effectors and signal transducers that regulate lysosome function and homeostasis.

Lastly, monitoring the actual changes in lysosomal PIP content in living cells remains a challenge. Although novel tools to monitor PIP lipids in living cells are emerging, these sensors often suffer from poor sensitivity and frequently fail to detect biologically active PIP pools as a result of competition with endogenous proteins (96). New high affinity sensors together with novel strategies to target them to the lysosome likely will allow for a better understanding of the role of PIPs in lysosome biology. These efforts may be paired with acute manipulations of lysosomal PIP content by the development of novel PIP binding probes and/ or chemical genetic approaches to rapidly alter PIP content at the lysosome surface (97). Insights generated from such studies and the development of new lysosomal PIP kinase and phosphatase inhibitors may pave the way for the treatment of human diseases caused by defective lysosomal PIP metabolism (9).

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Acknowledgements and Funding

We thank Dr. Barth Rossum (FMP) for help with the figure design. Work in the authors' laboratory was supported by grants from the German Funding Agency DFG (HA2686/15-1; TRR186/A08; TRR186/ A09), by a EMBO long term fellowship (LTF 285_2018), and a Leopoldina German National Academy of Sciences Postdoc fellowship (LPDS 2018_10).

Author contributions

The manuscript was written jointly by all authors.

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Legends to figures

Figure 1: Regulation of the life cycle and functions of lysosomes by PIP-metabolizing enzymes. INPP5E, inositol phosphate phosphatase 5E; mTORC1, mechanistic target of Rapamycin complex 1; OCRL, oculocerebrorenal syndrome of Lowe protein; PI4KII α or III β , phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase types II α or III β ; PIPK α/β or γ , phosphatidylinositol 4-phosphate 5-kinase type I α/β or γ ; VPS34, class III phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase; PIKfyve, FYVE domain-containing phosphatidylinositol 3-phosphate 5-kinase complex; PI3KC2 β , class II

phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase C2 β , PIP4KIIA, Phosphatidylinositol 5-phosphate 4-kinase type-2 α . See text for further details.

Figure 2: PIP regulation of lysosome function and homeostasis

(A) PIPs in the control of lysosome dynamics and signaling. In high nutrient conditions, the ER membrane protein Protrudin forms contact sites with lysosomes by interacting with lysosomal PI(3)P and Rab7. This leads to the transfer of kinesin-1 from protrudin to the PI(3)P and Rab7 effector FYCO1 and to (+)-end transport, resulting via unknown mechanisms in mTORC1 activation. Starvation induces the localization of PI3KC2 β to the Raptor subunit of mTORC1 on lysosomes and to the generation of PI(3,4)P₂. 14-3-3y associates with Raptor in a PI(3,4)P₂-dependent manner and inactivates mTORC1. Coincidence detection of Rab7 and PI(3,4)P₂ recruits the sterol transporter ORP1L to lysosomes (see also panel B). ORP1L is required for the association of Rab7 effector RILP to dynactin and (-)-end transport. PI(3,5)P₂ activates the Ca²⁺ release channel MCOLN1 and upon starvation MCOLN1-mediated local Ca²⁺ increases activate calcineurin, which leads to dephosphorylation and nuclear translocation of TFEB. In steady state conditions, PIKfyve activity contributes to retention of TFEB in the cytosol. At least in yeast, the mTORC1 subunit Raptor is an effector of PIKfyve. **(B)** PIP regulation of lysosomal sterol transport and membrane contact site formation with the ER. Coincidence detection of Rab7 and PI(3,4)P₂ generated by lysosomal PI3KC2 β are required for ORP1L and its binding partner ORP2 to transport cholesterol transport from lysosomes to the ER via membrane contact sites. Lysosomal cholesterol export is facilitated by the ORP5-associated lysosomal cholesterol transporter NPC1 and PI(4,5)P₂. **(C)** PIP regulation of autophagosome/ lysosome fusion. On autophagosomes, VPS34 complex I generates PI(3)P that together with the ATG5-12 complex recruits the protein TECPR1 to tether autophagosomes to lysosomes. Lysosomal PI(3)P synthesized by VPS34 complex II mediates the stabilization of actin filaments that facilitate the fusion process. On lysosomes, PI(3)P is converted to PI(3,5)P by PIKfyve and hydrolyzed by INPP5E. PI(4)P is generated on both, lysosomes and autophagosomes by PI4KII α . PI(4,5)P₂ is synthesized from PI(4)P by PIPKI on lysosomes and autolysosomes post-fusion. On lysosomes, PI(4,5)P₂ inhibits Rab7, triggering PLEKHM1 dissociation and fusion. On autolysosomes, PI(4,5)P₂ recruits clathrin/ AP-2 coats to induces lysosome reformation via budding of protolysosomes (see panel D). Clathrin/ AP-2 finally recruit the 5-phosphatase OCRL to autolysosomes to generate PI(4,5)P₂-free nanodomains containing active MCOLN1. **(D)** PIP regulation of lysosome tubulation and proto-lysosome formation. Starvation-induced synthesis of PI(4,5)P₂ on autolysosomes by PIPK α/β triggers clathrin/AP-2 coat assembly on tubules

pulled by kinesin 1/ KIF5B motors. Dynamin 2 facilitates the fission of proto-lysosomes. PI(3)P generated by VPS34 and PI(3,5)P₂ generated by PIKfyve are required for tubulation and reformation, FYCO1 and Spastizin are putative PI(3)P effectors implicated in these processes. PI(4)P generated by PI4KIIIβ inhibits tubulation.

Table 1: Inherited diseases related to defective lysosomal PIP metabolism

PIP	PIP-metabolizing enzyme	Function	Known or putative PIP effector(s)	Human disease(s)
PI(3)P	VPS34 (KINASE)	lysosome positioning	FYCO1	Autosomal-Recessive Congenital Cataracts
			Protrudin	Hereditary Spastic Paraplegia
		Autophagic lysosome reformation (ALR)	Spastizin, Spastacsin	Hereditary Spastic Paraplegia
	INPP5E (PHOSPHATASE)	Lysosome-autophagosome fusion		Joubert Syndrome, MORM syndrome
PI(4)P	PI4KII α (KINASE)	ALR, Lysosome and LRO biogenesis, Lysosome-autophagosome fusion		Hermanski-Pudlak Syndrome Gaucher's disease
	PI4KIII β (KINASE)	Lysosome Biogenesis		
	OCRL (PHOSPHATASE)	Autophagy		Lowe Syndrome
PI(3,5)P₂	PIKfyve/Vac14/Fig4 (KINASE-PHOSPHATASE complex)	ALR, lysosome positioning, LRO biology, nutrient signaling	MCOLN1, Raptor, vATPase, TPC2	Charcot-Marie Tooth Disease, Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, Mucopolysaccharidosis type IV, Fleck corneal dystrophy, Polymicrogyria, Yunis-Varon Syndrome, Pediatric-Onset Neurological Disease
			SNX14	Familial Cerebellar Atrophy
PI(4,5)P₂	PIPKI α/β (KINASE)	ALR, Lysosome-autophagosome fusion	KIF5B, AP2, Dynamin2, ATG14	Hereditary Spastic Paraplegia

Figure 1

Figure 2